

A MODIFIED DBSCAN ALGORITHM FOR TRAFFIC ACCIDENT CLUSTERING

JORDAN ATANASIJEVIĆ¹, DANIJELA PROTIĆ², DIMITRIJE KOLAŠINAC³, STEFAN IVANOVIĆ⁴,

¹ Center for Applied Mathematics and Electronics, Belgrade, Serbia, atanasijevicjordan@gmail.com, 0009-0003-0034-9974

² Center for Applied Mathematics and Electronics, Belgrade, Serbia, danijelaprotic318@gmail.com, 0000-0003-0827-2863

³ Center for Applied Mathematics and Electronics, Belgrade, Serbia, dimitrije.kolasinac@vs.rs, 0009-0008-9505-2482

⁴ Center for Applied Mathematics and Electronics, Belgrade, Serbia, stefanivanovic1012@gmail.com, 0009-0000-1788-2095

Abstract: Clustering is a machine learning approach used in wide range of scientific areas. The Density-Based Spatial Application with Noise (DBSCAN) algorithm creates clusters based on density. A modified DBSCAN (M-DBSCAN) algorithm is an upgraded version of the DBSCAN algorithm that incorporates weights as parameters to provide more precise cluster detection. Weights correspond to severities of traffic accidents. Road accidents resulting in minor injuries weight 1, road accidents resulting in serious injuries weight 10, and road accidents resulting in fatalities weight 85. The “Opasna mesta” application is developed to enable quick and convenient data management from the black spot database. The results of the experiments conducted on data on traffic roads from the Republic of Serbia reveal that M-DBSCAN provides better clustering results than DBSCAN algorithm.

Keywords: Density-based clustering, DBSCAN, modified-DBSCAN, traffic accidents.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the problems that follow the storage, processing and transmission of data have become a major research task and a significant challenge in daily business practice. Data analysis plays an important role in understanding different phenomena and can be used in a variety of research areas. Machine learning (ML) algorithms, which relate to statistical analysis focus on prediction, optimization and data analysis, are adaptive in a dynamic environment and can be evaluated in order to give correct results, even if the input parameters are (un)known. There are four basic types of ML model evaluation: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning. Clustering is an unsupervised machine learning technique that combines comparable data in clusters, according to their features. Cluster analysis can be used in various problem-solving methods (Xu et al., 2005). For this reason, many cluster analysis tools have been created, each of which has its own strengths and weaknesses, due to the complexity of the information (Rodriguez et al., 2019). A Density-Based Spatial Application with Noise (DBSCAN) algorithm identifies the clusters based on local data density (Singh et al., 2022). Its core parameters include maximum radius within which two points are considered neighbor in the same cluster ϵ , and the minimum number of points in the maximum distance, *MinPts*, required within that radius to define dense region to cluster formation. In this article, we introduce a modified DBSCAN algorithm (M-DBSCAN), which extends original framework by enhancing its applicability to multidimensional data. In addition to the spatial identifiers data which are used within DBSCAN, M-DBSCAN integrates both spatial identifiers and additional dataset attributes (numerical or textual) by transforming them into numerical values suitable for clustering. Furthermore, the weights are used alongside density-based criteria, for more precise distinction of clusters.

The spatial distribution of traffic accidents across a traffic network is not uniform. Road segments having a higher number of accidents, over a defined period, relative to the average of similar segments are considered dangerous. “Black spots” refer to specific areas or locations where traffic accidents involve fatalities, serious injuries and property damage are concentrated. Yadav et al. (2022) define a black spot as a 500-meter road stretch where either five traffic accidents resulted in fatalities and serious injuries occurred, or where 10 fatalities have been recorded within three-year period.

In this study the M-DBSCAN algorithm is applied to traffic accident data from the Republic of Serbia. To enhance clustering precision the algorithm assigns different weights to accident severity. Fatal accidents are weighted 85, serious injuries are weighted 10, and minor injuries accidents are weighted 1. The results show

that the M-DBSCAN algorithm is more precise and context-aware in high-risk traffic zones identification, compared to the standard DBSCAN algorithm.

2. RELATED WORK

The effectiveness of DBSCAN and in identifying high-risk zones and patterns within traffic networks, based on DBSCAN algorithm modification is proposed in Qui et al. (2016), Topcuoglu et al. (2022), and Li and Chen (2024), and Athanesious (2021). The researches underscore DBSCAN usage for traffic safety analysis, particularly when enhanced with domain-specific modifications and integrated with geospatial data. Qiu et al. (2016) proposed a modified DBSCAN algorithm for accident-prone locations detections on expressways in China. The authors emphasize spatial clustering accuracy and parameter sensitivity. In Topcuoglu et al. (2022), the authors analyzed the speed-related traffic accidents in Turkey, identifying clusters of dangerous road segments. Li and Chen (2024) examined road safety across Southeast Asia, and algorithm's adaptability in multi-criteria decision-making. In addition, Athanesious (2021) applied a DBSCAN-based anomaly detection framework, in the domain of traffic surveillance, to identify irregular vehicle trajectories from real-time monitoring video-data. Moreover, Khan et al. (2014) discuss the DBSCAN robustness to choice of input parameters.

Based on geospatial coordinates of traffic accidents database Wang et al. (2024) identified locations where traffic accidents tend to accumulate spatially, forming black spots. Black spots are also defined by Yadav et al. (2022) in terms of traffic accidents and/or fatalities recorded within three-year period.

3. DBSCAN ALGORITHM

A DBSCAN is a density-based clustering algorithm that identifies clusters of arbitrary shapes and sizes within a dataset. The DBSCAN algorithm groups points that are close to each other within a given radius, ignores isolated points, and recognizes clusters regardless of their form. The algorithm does not require the number of clusters to be determined a priori. However, despite its robustness to noise, adaptability to non-convex cluster shapes, and independence from predefined cluster counts, the DBSCAN performance is sensitive to the choice of input parameters, and computationally complex, that can be significant challenge for large-scale datasets (Khan et al., 2014). The DBSCAN algorithm operates based on the maximum distance between two points (one considered to be neighbor to the other) ϵ , and minimal number of other points $MinPts$ required to form dense region. Each data point can be classified as: core point (have at least $MinPts$ within a given distance ϵ), border point (lies within range of core point but do not have $MinPts$), or noise point (does not belong to any cluster). Users control how the algorithm defines clusters by adjusting $MinPts$ and ϵ .

The DBSCAN algorithm is a step-wise process of examining neighborhood of each point in the dataset to identify clusters based on the density of data points (Kumar, 2024), as follows:

- 1) Specify parameters $MinPts$ and ϵ
- 2) Select an arbitrary unvisited initial point
- 3) Examine the neighborhood
- 4) Expand the cluster if the point is core point
- 5) Repeat the process until all points have been processed
- 6) Finalize clusters
- 7) Address remained noise points

According to the Ester et al. (1996), ϵ is empirically best determined when $MinPts = 4$. To identify the cluster, the DBSCAN algorithm starts at the initial point p and recursively evaluates all points q that are density-reachable from p under the given parameters. If p is a central point, this procedure yields the cluster under the conditions ϵ and $MinPts$. If p is a boundary point, there are no density-reachable points, and the DBSCAN algorithm proceeds with the next candidate.

The DBSCAN algorithm is highly effective anomaly and noise detection, clustering radar reflection, mapping disease epicenters, customer segmentation, storm tracking, and geospatial event detection of global positioning system (GPS) – based locations, including the assessment of traffic safety factors that influence the occurrence of traffic accidents and accumulation of traffic accidents with similar characteristics.

4. MODIFIED DBSCAN ALGORITHM

When consider locations with a high risk of accidents, there are no standardized methods to identify black spots on the roads. The huge amount of data is a great challenge, although there is a number of mechanisms that enable the best decision possible. In modified DBSCAN, weights are assigned to each accident based on

severity and frequency. These weights influence the density estimation by adjusting the effective neighborhood radius per point. The algorithm is based on a parameterized mathematical model for identification of clusters (i.e. areas) around black spots, using data of the geographical position in which the accidents occurred and type of accidents, which can include injuries and/or fatalities. Unlike the DBSCAN, the M-DBSCAN operates under the assumption that, in addition to spatial identification, a weight can be assign to the point for which cluster is being sought (Eq. 1).

$$w_i = \alpha \cdot S_i + \beta \cdot F_i, \quad (1)$$

where S_i is the normalized severity score, F_i is the local frequency of similar accidents. The parameters α and β control the relative influence of each factor. This formulation allows the algorithm to prioritize high-impact of frequency occurring incidents during clustering. Eq. 1 aggregates weights to normalize the distribution but each instance receive its own weight.

Based on geospatial coordinates of traffic accidents database (publicly available data set downloaded from <https://data.gov.rs/sr/datasets/podatsi-o-saobratshajnim-nezgodama-po-politsijskim-upravama-i-opshtinama/>, 2025) it was possible to identify locations where traffic accidents tend to accumulate spatially, forming black spots (Wang et al., 2024). The coordinates along with accident-specific attributes serve as inputs to the M-DBSCAN algorithm that includes both density and severity. Unlike standard DBSCAN, the M-DBSCAN does not require the number of clusters to be known in advance, which is ideal for large, unstructured datasets. The severities of road accidents are defined by the International Road Workers' Association (PIARC, 2008), as follows: road accidents involving minor injuries – weight 1, road accidents involving serious injuries – weight 10, and road accidents with fatalities – weight 85. The clusters identified around black spots are determined as follows:

$$WNI = 85 \cdot n_{fatalities} + 10 \cdot n_{serious_injuries} + n_{minor_injuries}, \quad (2)$$

where WNI is the Weighted Number of traffic-accidents Indicator within a specified radius, and $n_{fatalities}$, $n_{serious_injuries}$, and $n_{minor_injuries}$ represent numbers of road accidents with fatalities, seriously injured persons, and participants with minor injuries, respectively.

The M-DBSCAN algorithm proceeds through the following steps:

1. *Parameter initialization*: cluster radius r , cumulative cluster radius $r_{sum} = 0$, threshold k , weights assigned to each data point, cumulative distance sum within potential cluster $Suma=0$, number of internal clusters $b_{uk}=0$, number of external clusters $b_{sk}=0$, and the incremental cluster radius value $d=0$, which will be updated in subsequent iterations.
2. *The algorithm calculates the sum of weighted values within each cluster* defined by r , and checks whether any previously identified clusters exist. If overlapping clusters are detected, they are merged until only one remains.
3. *Weight assignment* based on severity and frequency attributes.
4. *Pairwise distance calculation* for every data point to all other points in the data set.
5. *Cluster evaluation*. Calculate the sum of weighted values within the initially defined cluster. Clusters that satisfy condition $Suma \geq k$ are identified and subsequently analyzed in the following step.
6. *Clusters comparison and selection*. Compare analyzed cluster with those meeting threshold condition, in descending order of their total weighted values. If two clusters to overlap, the less independent cluster (i.e. the one with the lower $Suma$). There are two scenarios in decisions
 - a) *The center of a cluster lies within the radius of the other cluster*. The cluster with the lower weighted value is rejected and the internal cluster count is updated as: $b_{uk} = b_{uk} + 1$.
 - b) *Two clusters overlap, but the center of one cluster lies outside the radius of the other cluster*. The cluster with the lower total value is discarded. The cumulative radius is updated $r_{sum} = r_{sum} + d - r$, and the external cluster count is incremented: $b_{sk} = b_{sk} + 1$.
7. *Iteration and stopping criteria*. If not overlap is detected than compute $d = r_{sum}/b_{sk}$. The algorithm then iterates through all clusters, repeating steps 4 and 5 until clusters with the largest distances are identified.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To demonstrate the advantages of the M-DBSCAN algorithm, the experiments were conducted using open database on traffic accidents in Serbia. The geostatistical and spatial analysis were applied to open data, based

on the ArcGIS Pro environment. A detailed overview of the ArcGIS Pro is available at <https://data.gov.rs> while the structure of the open dataset is described in the work of Gladović & Deretić (2018).

To facilitate practical data management, custom application named *Opasna mesta* was developed. Its main interface includes six combo-boxes (*Opšti podaci o putu*, *Opasna mesta*, *Saobraćajne nezgode*, *Saobraćaj*, *Izveštaji* and *Pomoć*) and three command buttons (*Dijagram saobraćajnih nezgoda*, *Radovi na putu* and *Odjava*). The application retrieves data from all recorded traffic accidents via national open data portal, covering incidents across Serbia from 2015 to the present. Users can filter results by city, search radius, minimum *WNI* value, and time period based on attributes stored in a relational database.

Using geospatial coordinates, the M-DBSCAN algorithm identifies coordinates with concentrated occurrence of traffic accidents. It begins by extracting spatial coordinates and accident types to assign severity weight to each location within a 300m radius, focusing on period from 2022 to 2024. Hazardous road segments are ranked in descending order, according to the *WNI* (see Eq. 2). If $WNI \geq 85$, the algorithm proceeds with in-depth analysis of this cluster. According to the defined procedure, all points meeting or exceeding defined threshold undergo further evaluation. Pairwise distances between points are then calculated and, if the distance is less than 300 meters, the weighted values are added to the cluster sum. In the next step, the cluster radius is incrementally expanded based on the average value of surrounding clusters. In this study, the maximum radius was 479 meters; once the radius exceeds 500m, the algorithm terminates. Figure 1 illustrates the results for municipality of Arilje. The standard DBSCAN identified a single black spot (dashed red circle) whereas M-DBSCAN detected two distinct black spots in the same area, demonstrating its enhanced sensitivity and clustering precision.

Figure 1: Black spots in the area of Arilje (2022-2024)

As it is noted before, the M-DBSCAN algorithm generates a highly detailed spatial map due to the increased number of clusters it identifies. Figure 2 illustrates this effect by presenting both the centroids (left) and the corresponding clusters of black spots detected in the Belgrade area. This example highlights the algorithm's enhanced sensitivity in distinguishing multiple high-risk zones within dense urban environments, offering a more granular view compared to standard clustering.

Figure 2: Centroids (left) and black spots identified in Belgrade area

6. CONCLUSION

Clustering techniques are useful for extracting knowledge from a large amount of geospatial data. The DBSCAN algorithm is density-based algorithm that forms clusters on the basis of non-dense and dense regions. The most important parameters of the DBSCAN algorithm are the maximum distance between two points in the same cluster and the minimum number of points in the maximum distance between two points to form a cluster. The M-DBSCAN algorithm is a modified version of the DBSCAN algorithm. The algorithm is based on the assumption that the points for which clusters are sought, in addition to spatial identification, have weights that refer to severity of road accidents. Traffic accidents are weighted according to severity: incidents resulting in minor injuries carry a weight of 1, accidents involving serious injuries are assigned a weight of 10, while accidents with fatalities are given the highest weight of 85. The identified black spots are ranked according to the value of the *WNI*. All spots whose *WNI* are equal to or greater than the specified threshold are considered potential black spots and are subject to further analyses. The key advantage of the algorithm lies in its ability to operate without prior specification of the number of clusters, while it achieves more precise cluster identification by including weights as additional parameters for clustering.

In order to enable a simple and comfortable data management, a user-friendly application called *Opasna mesta* was developed. It is shown that the M-DBSCAN algorithm generates a highly detailed spatial map due to the increased number of clusters it identifies. The algorithm's enhanced sensitivity is useful in distinguishing multiple high-risk zones within given environments.

In our further work we will consider using the M-DBSCAN in two directions. First, we intend to apply this algorithm in the area that are not related to the spatial clustering. The idea is to use the different types of publicly available data. The other direction is to use the M-DBSCAN algorithm in various scientific areas, such as data protection in preserving sensitive datasets (medical records, financial logs) to protect secure similar computation for clustering user behavior without revealing the user activity patterns, and AI-driven feature selection to detect anomalies without exposing the raw traffic. The intention is also to integrate the M-DBSCAN algorithm with artificial intelligence, to improve algorithms for feature selection, such as Artificial Rabbit Optimization (ARO)-DBSCAN.

LITERATURE

- Athanesious, J. J. (2021). Anomaly detection using DBSCAN in traffic video surveillance. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356789012_Anomaly_Detection_Using_DBSCAN_in_Traffic_Video_Surveillance
- Ester, M., Kriegel, H., Sander, J., & Xu, X. (1996). A density-based algorithm for discovering clusters in large spatial databases with noise. *Inkdd*, 96(34), 226-231.
- Gladović, P., & Deretić, N. (2018). Otvoreni podaci i baze podataka u analizi saobraćajnih nezgoda u gradu Beogradu. *Tehnika*, 73(2), 247-253.
- Li, J., & Chen, F. (2024). A hybrid EWM-PROMETHEE II-DBSCAN model for road safety monitoring. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12, 1413031.
- Khan, K., Rehman, S., Aziz, K., Fong, S., & Sarasvady, S. (2014). DBSCAN: Past, present and future. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on the Applications of Digital Information and Web Technologies*, 17-19 February 2014, Bangalore, India. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICADIWT.2014.6814687>
- Kumar, R. (2024). A guide to the DBSCAN clustering algorithm. <https://www.datacamp.com/tutorial/dbscan-clustering-algorithm>
- PIARC. (2008). *Road safety manual. Recommendation from the World Road Association*. Chapter 7.
- Podaci o saobraćajnim nezgodama po policijskim upravama i opštinama. (2025). <https://data.gov.rs/sr/datasets/podatsi-o-saobratshajnim-nezgodama-po-politsijskim-upravama-i-opshtinama/>
- Qiu, C., Xu, H., & Bao, Y. (2016). A modified DBSCAN algorithm for identifying traffic accident prone locations. *In IDEAL 2016 – Intelligent Data Engineering and Automated Learning*, 106–114. Springer, Cham.
- Rodriguez, M., Comin, C., Casanova, D., Bruno, O., Armancio, D., da F. Costa, L., & Rodriguez, F. (2019). Clustering algorithms: A comparative approach. *PloS One*, 14(1), e0210236. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0210236>

- Singh, H., Girdhar, A., & Dahya, S. (2022). A literature survey based on DBSCAN algorithms. *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems*, 25-27 May 2022, Madurai, India, 751-758. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICCS53718.2022.9788440>
- Topcuoglu, B., Memisoglu Baykal, T., & Tuydes Yaman, H. (2022). GIS-based DBSCAN and NNH clustering for speed-related traffic accident analysis. *ISPRS Archives, XLVIII-4/W1-2022*, 487–492.
- Wang, Y., Zhao, Q., Xiu, W. (2024). Blackspot identification of abnormal driving behavior based on improved DBSCAN algorithm. *Proceedings of the 3rd Conference on Electronic Information Engineering, Big Data, and Computer Technology*, 13181, 292-299.
- Xu, R., & Wunsch, D. (2005). Survey on clustering algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, 16(3), 645-678. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNN.2005.845141>
- Yadav, D. K., Ghodmare, S. D., & Kumar, N. N. (2022). Mitigation of Blackspots on Highways by the Application of Safe System Approach. *Proceedings of Materials Today*, 52, 1228-1235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.11.042>

APPENDIX

Data on traffic accidents from 2022 to 2024 are available at: <https://data.gov.rs/sr/datasets/podatsi-o-saobratshajnim-nezgodama-po-politsijskim-upravama-i-opshtinama/>,

The M-DBSCAN algorithm implementation and user-selected parameters from the relational dataset are available upon request from the corresponding author.